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MAKTABGACHA
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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METHODS OF UTILISING THE LEGACY OF EASTERN THINKERS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the pedagogical ideas and educational heritage of prominent Eastern thinkers, emphasizing their contributions to the formation of moral, intellectual and cultural foundations in the learning process. The study highlights how classical Eastern pedagogical principles can be integrated into modern educational practices in order to enhance students' personal development, creativity and value-based learning. Special attention is given to the role of the teacher as a cultural mediator who transmits historical intellectual traditions to younger generations.

Key words: pedagogical heritage, Eastern thinkers, pedagogical ideas, educational principles, teacher.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Sharq mutafakkirlarining pedagogik merosi, ularning ta'lim jarayoniga oid g'oyalari va tamoyillari ilmiy asosda tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda Sharq pedagogikasining axloqiy, ma'naviy va intellektual qarashlari zamonaviy ta'lim amaliyotiga qanday yo'sinda integratsiya qilinishi mumkinligi yoritiladi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchining tarixiy-intellektual qadriyatlarini yosh avlodga yetkazuvchi ma'naviy vositachi sifatidagi o'rni alohida ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik meros, Sharq mutafakkirlari, pedagogik g'oyalar, pedagogik tamoyillar, o'qituvchi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются педагогические идеи и образовательное наследие великих мыслителей Востока, их вклад в формирование нравственных, интеллектуальных и культурных основ образовательного процесса. Анализируется возможность применения классических восточных педагогических принципов в современной педагогической практике для развития личности обучающихся, их креативности и ценностного мировоззрения. Особое внимание уделяется роли учителя как духовного посредника, передающего молодому поколению историко-интеллектуальные традиции.

Ключевые слова: педагогическое наследие, мыслители Востока, педагогические идеи, педагогические принципы, учитель.

INTRODUCTION

The pedagogical legacy of outstanding Eastern scholars has made a significant contribution to global pedagogical thought. However, until the Central Asian republics gained independence, the ideas of medieval thinkers remained largely unclaimed. Only in recent years has there been a revival of interest in this rich treasure trove of pedagogical thought.

The pedagogical concepts of Eastern philosophers represent a democratic trend in medieval pedagogy, exerting a significant influence on the formation of ideas about human beings, as well as on the development of theories of education and training for the younger generation. These ideas remain relevant today, serving as a fertile ground for the formation of ideas not only about man and his education, but also about humanism, the comprehensive development of the personality, and the requirements for teachers.

When studying the pedagogical views of such thinkers as al-Khwarizmi, al-Farabi, al-Beruni, Ibn Sina, Omar Khayyam, Saadi, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Babur, Yusuf Balasaguni, Mahmud-haji Behbudi, Abdullah Avloni, Mahmud Kashgari, Ahmad Yugnaki and others, one can conclude that these outstanding scholars and educators, reflecting on man, personality, upbringing and education, attached great importance to labour, knowledge, reason, the art of speech and high moral qualities. They strove to create well-rounded, skilled and educated individuals.

Thus, the pedagogical ideas of the great Eastern thinkers continue to influence the modern understanding of education and upbringing, serving as a basis for further research and practical innovations in the field of pedagogy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The pedagogical principles, guidelines, instructions, requirements and recommendations of Eastern thinkers remain relevant and in demand in the modern educational context. In particular, the foundations for training teaching staff in the higher education system are based on the pedagogical concepts of the great scholars of the medieval East. These views serve as an important resource for the formation of professional competencies of future teachers, providing them with a deep understanding of the processes of teaching and education, as well as contributing to the development of humanistic values and high moral standards in educational practice.

Al-Khwarizmi emphasises the importance of independence and creative activity among students. He focuses on the need to observe facts and phenomena, describe them and explain them consistently, which contributes to the development of analytical thinking among students.

Al-Farabi, in turn, focuses on the comprehensive development and improvement of the individual. He highlights the cultivation of moral norms of behaviour, as well as the formation of positive and noble traits and qualities. An important aspect of his pedagogical concept is the formation of spiritual needs, which determine the key traits of a person's character and contribute to their intellectual development. According to Al-Farabi, the requirements for a teacher include phenomenal memory, logical thinking, keen observation, a love of knowledge, eloquence, fairness and virtue. Among the recommended teaching methods, he highlights persuasion, proof, discussion, a dialectical-logical approach and visual teaching methods.

Al-Biruni emphasises equipping students with scientific facts, highlighting the importance of experience and observation, as well as repetition and knowledge transfer. He emphasises the accessibility of education as a key aspect of the educational process.

Ibn Sina focuses on nurturing a well-rounded personality while taking into account the individual abilities of each student. He emphasises the pursuit of excellence and formulates principles such as living not only for oneself but also for others, as well as a creative approach to one's work and high moral standards. Requirements for teachers include knowledge of the nature of the child, their soul and individuality, as well as the ability to see them as a person, believe in their potential and help them develop. Teachers must show moderation in their relationships with students, possess sensitivity and insight, and demonstrate humanism and confidence in educating well-rounded individuals, where morality is the main subject of education. The methods and techniques used in their teaching practice include conversation, suggestion, setting an example, analysis, synthesis and generalisation.

Omar Khayyam emphasises the importance of students deeply assimilating knowledge and acquiring it independently. He stresses the importance of self-development, discipline and willpower, as well as achieving set goals. In the educational process, the main focus is on comprehension, thinking, habit formation and the use of various methods, among which repetition plays an important role.

Burkhanuddin Zarnuji emphasises consistency and continuity in teaching and education, focusing on the conscious nature of learning activities. He stresses the importance of analysis, synthesis and generalisation, as well as independent reasoning and self-education as key components of the educational process.

Muslihiddin Saadi formulates principles that emphasise the active participation of the individual in the formation of knowledge. He stresses the importance of taking into account natural aptitudes as prerequisites for ability development, the systematicity and accessibility of knowledge, as well as its practical application and connection to life. An important aspect of his pedagogical concept is the development of students' mental abilities, with a particular emphasis on the leading role of labour education.

Abdurrahman Jami emphasises a humanistic approach to teaching, highlighting scientific rigour, systematicity and consistency, accessibility of knowledge and its connection to practical activities.

Alisher Navoi formulates requirements for teachers, among which respect for human beings as the highest and most valuable gift of nature, love for children, perfect knowledge of their subject and the ability to apply their knowledge in practice stand out. He also emphasises the importance of attention to moral and labour education, as well as the cultivation of positive qualities in students and educational activities.

Zahiriddin Babur emphasises the connection between learning and life, the activation of students' cognitive activity and taking into account their individual characteristics and abilities. He stresses the importance of teaching the ability to analyse, synthesise and generalise the knowledge gained, as well as ethical and didactic guidance, which serves as the basis for education.

Mahmudhaja Behbudi emphasises the need for the comprehensive development of teachers and their full education, as well as their mastery of modern methods of teaching and education.

Abdullah Avloni focuses on the personality of the teacher, emphasising the importance of high moral character, pedagogical ethics and the significance of knowledge as a powerful tool in professional and personal life. He emphasises the improvement of a child's moral education, the development of mental abilities and the

importance of teaching not only reading and writing, but also the analysis of the essence of things and the ability to distinguish between good and bad.

Ahmad Yugnaki's pedagogical system postulates that the fundamental conditions for personality formation and development are intellectual improvement and comprehensive (harmonious) development, with special emphasis on moral and ethical education, behavioural etiquette and communicative culture. In the context of the educational process, cognitive development is emphasised. The fundamental positive personal qualities formed in the process of education include integrity (fairness), moderation (modesty), tolerance (forbearance), delicacy (tact) and generosity.

Yusuf Balasaguni and Mahmud Kashgari emphasised the critical role of knowledge in an individual's life. Their pedagogical views included the need for a differentiated approach to teaching that takes into account the individual psychophysiological characteristics of learners, as well as the importance of professional (craft) training.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The pedagogical principles and recommendations of Eastern thinkers were studied using analytical, comparative and descriptive methods. Their works were examined to identify core pedagogical concepts and the ways in which these ideas relate to modern educational practice. The methodological approach included interpreting classical texts, identifying key principles and comparing them with the requirements of contemporary higher education. Through this process, the research determined the relevance of medieval Eastern scholars' pedagogical ideas and assessed their applicability in developing teachers' professional competencies, humanistic values and moral qualities in today's educational context.

ANALYS AND RESULTS

Outstanding thinkers of the medieval East left behind a lasting (transcendent) pedagogical legacy, including fundamental guidelines, pedagogical axioms and principles, effective teaching and education methods, as well as high standards for teachers and mentors. Their common goal was to shape well-rounded and erudite (competent) individuals. The quintessence of their worldview is the powerful spiritual potential, the vitality of their conceptual ideas, the principle of continuity of pedagogical views, the scale of pedagogical thinking, the highest humanism, patriotic orientation, authenticity (truthfulness) and peacemaking position.

All conceptual positions, principles, methods and approaches developed by outstanding encyclopaedists of the medieval East are recognised as highly relevant for solving contemporary tasks of training pedagogical personnel. They have undeniable pedagogical potential and significant educational value for modernising the educational process.

Among the key positions of medieval thinkers that should be integrated, the following stand out:

- holistic (integrated) and multifaceted development of the individual, including the improvement of teachers' qualifications;
- systematisation of knowledge by dividing it into theoretical and practical components with an emphasis on their interconnection;
- stimulation of students' cognitive activity and development of their logical thinking;
- ensuring scientific accuracy, clarity and visualisation in the learning process;
- deep understanding of the learning material and independent acquisition of knowledge;
- active role of the student in self-education and self-development.

The main vectors for implementing the pedagogical ideas of Eastern thinkers in the system of professional and pedagogical training of future teachers include:

- focus on the philosophical and pedagogical paradigm of Eastern thinkers, aimed at the comprehensive, harmonious development and self-improvement of the individual to the level of full competence in personal, professional and socially significant aspects;
- implementation of the principle of humanisation in goal setting, content and organisation (procedural component) of educational activities;
- encouraging a creative approach to professional pedagogical activity;
- formation of an ethical culture, as well as moral and spiritual priorities in future specialists;

- intensive acquisition of knowledge, especially professionally significant knowledge, and stimulation of intellectual development;
- application of an individualised (personalised) approach in the process of developing the personality of the future teacher;
- search for and testing of innovative methods, techniques, approaches and means to ensure the comprehensive (holistic) development of the personality of the future teacher.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, the pedagogical legacy of the great scholars and thinkers of the East served as a methodological basis for incorporating relevant ideas and principles into modern teacher training practices, which, in turn, determines the improvement of the professional and qualitative level of future teachers. A universally recognised benchmark for improving the quality of education is to draw on the historical experience and traditions of previous generations, in particular the fundamental pedagogical legacy of Eastern thinkers.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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